

Kinetics of the Reaction between Activated Aliphatic and Aromatic Halides with Oxygen Nucleophiles- Study of some Linear free Energy Relationships

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The rates of reaction between sodium aliphatic carboxylates with phenacyl bromide and picryl chloride have been measured in aqueous acetone. The activation parameters have been computed. The kinetic data, plotted in a Brønsted fashion, against pK_a values of the nucleophiles, yield a sigmoid plot in case of phenacyl bromide and linear plot in case of picryl chloride. The rate data have been fitted into Taft equation and the steric parameters have been computed. The linear relationship between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger have been observed.

CONANT, Kirner and Hussey¹ first called attention to the profound influence of Y groups on the reactivity of YCH_2-Cl type halides towards postassium iodide in acetone. The powerful activating effect of the carbonyl, cyano and related groups in this and other SN_2 reactions has since been the subject of much study and speculation²⁻⁶. Earlier we have reported the SN_2 reaction of phenacyl bromide with aromatic amines⁷⁻⁹ and sodium salts of some *meta*- and *para*-substituted aromatic acids¹⁰. In the present case, we wish to report the SN_2 reaction of some active aliphatic and aromatic halides with sodium salts of certain aliphatic acids. Attempts have been made to use some of the linear free energy equations, which may throw light to the nature of transition state. The active halides chosen were phenacyl bromide and picryl chloride.

Experimental

Analar acetone was diluted to the required volume with triple distilled water.

Phenacyl bromide was prepared and purified by the method of Ruther and Reid¹³. Picryl chloride (BDH) was crystallised from alcohol-light petroleum. The ethanolic solution of the slight excess of the acid was mixed with the ethanolic sodium ethoxide. The sodium salt was filtered, washed with ethanol, and then dried in vacuo to a constant weight in a tarred flask at 100°-110°.

Kinetic Measurements

The SN_2 reactions at different temperatures were followed by pipetting 5 ml aliquots in a 10 ml of 5% aqueous nitric acid and then titrating the halide ion by the Volhard's method, after partition between 15 ml benzene, 10 ml water and 5 ml of silver nitrate solution. The aqueous layer together with 2 x 10 ml washings were titrated with ammonium thiocyanate solution. Second order rate constants were calculated by least-squares using Tobey's method¹³. The standard deviation of the individual plot was usually within 1% and agreement between duplicate was within 1-2%. The maximum error in the activation parameters is ± 0.5 K Cal mole⁻¹ for the enthalpy of activation and ± 0.8 e.u. for the entropy of activation¹⁴.

Results and Discussion

Effect of substituents on rate

The kinetic results obtained for all the substituents indicate good agreement with second order kinetics according to the relationships

$$k_t = \frac{2.303}{t(a-b)} \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$$

where a and b are the concentrations of activated halides and sodium carboxylates respectively. The rate of the reaction increases with lengthening the chain of the carbon atoms in the aliphatic series.

Activation parameters

The activation parameters have been computed. The values of enthalpy of activation decrease with lengthening the carbon chain in both the reactions. The large negative entropy of activation is as expected for bimolecular reactions with highly polar transition state¹⁵. An additional contribution to the activation parameters from solvation effect is suggested by the observed variation in ΔS^\ddagger .

Relationship between basicity and SN_2 reactivity-Brønsted relationship: The significance of Brønsted relationship is well recognised¹⁶⁻²³. The correlation between basicity and nucleophilicity has been represented graphically by plotting the logarithm of the rate constants against the pK_a values²⁴ of the corresponding conjugate acids in water. A curve is obtained in case of phenacyl bromide. This type of sigmoid plot is very unusual²⁵ in case of the Brønsted correlation although mechanistic changes have been suggested in case of the sigmoid plot of the Hammett correlation²⁶. A more quantitative linear free-energy relationship might be expected for aliphatic SN_2 reactivity.

A slope of 0.32 was found for the reaction of sodium salts of aliphatic acids with picryl chloride. A slope of 0.50 was found for the reaction of *para* and *meta* substituted sodium benzoates with phenacyl bromide¹⁰. The value of Brønsted coefficient computed for the reaction of substituted anilines with phenacyl bromide⁷ and *m*-nitrophenacyl bromide^{7,8} were found to be 1.1

and 0.85 respectively. Further, the value of the Brönsted coefficient was computed to be 1.25 for the reaction of nitrogen nucleophiles with picryl chloride²⁷. These values are considerably higher than for the reaction of phenacyl bromide and picryl chloride with oxygen nucleophiles. The Brönsted slopes are therefore characteristic of the nucleophiles. The obvious conclusion seems to be that with oxygen nucleophiles there is very little bond formation in the transition state while with nitrogen nucleophiles the bond formation is stronger and S_AN mechanism is operative²⁸.

Application of Taft equation ; The application of Taft equation was examined by plotting the graph between the logarithm of the rate constants against σ^{\neq} and E_s values²⁹ both in case of picryl chloride and phenacyl bromide. Linear plots were obtained in both the cases. The values of δ and ρ^{\neq} were calculated to be 1.45, 4 and 3.2, 2.2 for phenacyl bromide and picryl chloride respectively. The positive values of ρ indicate that with increases of chain length, the rate is enhanced. Making use of the constants, a four parameter equation¹¹ can be envisaged for the reaction of sodium salts of aliphatic acids with activated aliphatic and aromatic halides,

$$\log k/k_0 = 3.2 \sigma^{\neq} + 1.45 E_s \text{ (Phenacyl bromide)}$$

$$\log k/k_0 = 2.2 \sigma^{\neq} + 4 E_s \text{ (Picryl chloride)}$$

Steric factor is more pronounced in case of aromatic SN₂ reaction. This is because of the fact that the transition state is more crowded in case of aromatic SN₂ reaction than with aliphatic reactivities³⁰.

The Isokinetic relationship : A linear relationship between the entropy of activation (ΔS^{\neq}) and the enthalpy of activation (ΔH^{\neq}) has been observed for the reaction of the nucleophiles both with phenacyl bromide and picryl chloride. The values of ' β ', the isokinetic temperatures were computed to be 580 and 630 for phenacyl bromide and picryl chloride. The significance that is attached to the isokinetic temperature³¹ is that at this temperature all the substituents should have the same rate coefficients if similar mechanism is operative. The higher value of ' β ' for picryl chloride indicates that in case of activated aromatic halides the effect of substituents on rate may apparently be same at higher temperature than with aliphatic SN₂ reactivities.

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE WITH CARBOXYLATE IONS IN 90% (VOL/VOL) AQUEOUS ACETONE.

[Phenacyl bromide] = 0.08 (M); [Sodium carboxylate] = 0.04 (M)

Carboxylate ion	k × 10 ³ l. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹		
	30°	35°	35°
Caproate	8.95	11.83	15.85
Valerate	7.0	9.30	13.23
Propionate	6.24	8.51	12.60
Acetate	2.74	4.04	6.03
Mono chloroacetate	1.45	2.29	3.56
Formate	1.26	2.00	3.10

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION OF PHENACYL BROMIDE WITH CARBOXYLATE IONS IN 90% (VOL/VOL) AQUEOUS ACETONE.

Carboxylate ions	E _a K. Cal mole ⁻¹	log A	-ΔS [‡] 30° Cal mole ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	-ΔH [‡] K. Cal mole ⁻¹
Caproate	11.00	7.50	33.60	10.40
Valerate	11.60	7.94	32.50	10.90
Propionate	12.00	8.20	31.00	11.40
Acetate	14.80	9.90	23.30	13.20
Mono chloro acetate	17.00	11.30	17.30	16.40
Formate	18.00	11.90	14.0	17.40

TABLE 3—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE REACTION OF PICRYL CHLORIDE WITH CARBOXYLATE IONS IN 60% (VOL/VOL) AQUEOUS ACETONE.

[Picryl chloride] = 0.025 (M); [Carboxylate ions] = 0.05 (M)

Carboxylate ions	k × 10 ⁸ l. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹		
	25°	30°	35°
Propionate	3.38	5.52	7.37
Acetate	1.84	2.92	4.91
Formate	1.68	2.30	3.99
Mono chloro acetate	0.422	0.998	1.84

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE REACTION OF PICRYL CHLORIDE WITH CARBOXYLATE IONS IN 60% (VOL/VOL) AQUEOUS ACETONE.

Carboxylate ions	E _a K. Cal mole ⁻¹	log A	-ΔS [‡] 30° Cal mole ⁻¹ K ⁻¹	ΔH [‡] K. Cal mole ⁻¹
Propionate	13.80	7.60	25.50	13.20
Acetate	17.50	10.00	14.40	16.90
Formate	18.90	10.90	10.20	18.30
Mono chloro acetate	24.40	14.50	6.20	24.80

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T. R. MOHANTY, (Mrs) P. MISHRA & P. L. NAYAK : KINETICS OF THE REACTION BETWEEN ACTIVATED

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